

(REVIEW ARTICLE)

The effect of authoritative parenting style on individual development: A literature review

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World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews, 2024, 21(01), 205–209

Publication history: Received on 18 November 2023; revised on 27 December 2023; accepted on 29 December 2023

Article DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/wjarr.2024.21.1.2662>

Abstract

Authoritative parenting style is a parenting style that emphasizes a close relationship between parents and their children through affection, disciplinary action is not a punishment but a way to guide, provide advice on the direction of life goals through good communication. The purpose of this study was to determine the effect of authoritative parenting on individual development. This study uses a literature review method sourced from national scientific journal articles obtained through Science Direct, Google Scholar, and Pubmed. This study shows that authoritative parenting is associated with cognitive development, behavior problems, career decision self-efficacy of adolescents, empathy development, life satisfaction, social skills, emotional problems, self-esteem and approach coping strategies.

Keywords: Parenting style; Authoritative; Democratic; Individual development

1. Introduction

In recent decades, a large proportion of the lay public, academics and policy makers have affirmed the role of parenting style's relationship with positive adaptation to promote individuals' positive development and well-being (1). Authoritative parenting style is considered to be cooperative, supportive, coercive parenting while also being guiding, supportive and helpful (2). Authoritative parenting style is a parenting style that emphasizes a close relationship between parents and their children through affection, disciplinary action not as a punishment but a way to guide, provide advice on the direction of life goals through good communication (3). Parenting style will determine and support an individual's intellectual, emotional, physical, and social development (2). In general, individuals with authoritative parents have personalities with a high level of self-confidence, are responsible, able to make decisions, have high self-esteem and are able to manage emotions and a high social spirit. Whereas the authoritarian pattern shows the opposite result (3). Fewer difficulties are experienced by children raised in an authoritative style, while the opposite relationship is shown by the authoritarian style (1). In addition, authoritative parenting style is positively associated with cognitive development and academic achievement (4,5). Given this, it is important to discuss authoritative parenting on individual development.

2. Material and methods

This article used the literature review method, which is a search of literature from national scientific journal articles and published in the last five years (2018-2023) obtained through Google Scholar, ScienceDirect and Pubmed databases. The search for literature used several keywords, namely "authoritative", "democratic", "parenting style", "individual development", "child development" and "adolescent development". In the search for literature also used boolean tools so that the articles obtained are neither too narrow nor too wide. The inclusion criteria for this study include using

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English, open access, last five years, and the original article. After the screening, 11 articles are selected to qualify for review.

3. Results and discussion

Based on the collected and analyzed articles, the findings are presented as follows:

Table 1 List of Articles

No.	Author	Research Title	Method	Result
1.	Julia Theresya, Melly Latifah and Neti Hernawati	The Effect of Parenting Style, Self-Efficacy, and Self Regulated Learning on Adolescents' Academic Achievement	Cross sectional study	There is a positive and significant correlation between gender ($r=0,317$, $p\text{-value} <0,01$), birth order ($r=0,282$, $p\text{-value} <0,01$) and family number ($r= 0,337$, $p\text{-value} <0,01$) with authoritarian parenting styles. Authoritative parenting style ($r=0.257$, $p\text{-value} <0.05$) and self-efficacy ($r=0.330$, $p\text{-value} <0.01$) are positively and significantly related to self-regulated learning. In addition, there is a positive influence between father's education ($\beta=0.315$, $p\text{-value}=0.006$) and authoritative parenting styles ($\beta=0.259$, $p\text{-value}=0.014$) on academic achievement, while having a negative influence is gender ($\beta=-0.267$, $p\text{-value}= 0.014$) and permissive parenting style($\beta =-0.203$, $p\text{-value}=0.039$) (4).
2.	Elisa Delvecchio, Alessandro Germani, Veronica Raspa, Adriana Lis and Claudia Mazzeschi	Parenting Styles and Child's Well-Being: The Mediating Role of the Perceived Parental Stress	Regression and moderation analysis	Less difficulty is experienced by children raised in the authoritative style, while the opposite relationship is shown by the authoritarian style (1).
3.	Wang, L., Xian, Y., Dill, S. E., Fang, Z., Emmers, D., Zhang, S., & Rozelle, S.	Parenting style and the cognitive development of preschool-aged children: Evidence from rural China	Multivariate regression model	Authoritative parenting style was positively associated with children's cognitive development, while the opposite relationship was shown by authoritarian style. In addition, these parenting styles were more strongly correlated in girls than boys (5).
4.	Dominikus David Biondi Situmorang and Rose Mini Agoes Salim	Perceived parenting styles, thinking styles, and gender on the career decision self-efficacy of adolescents: how & why?	Non-experimental quantitative	Authoritative parenting styles from mothers and fathers have a significant and positive effect on career decision self-efficacy of adolescents. In addition, career decision self-efficacy of adolescents is also influenced by 3 types of thinking styles (type 1, type 2 and type 3) (6).
5.	Divna Haslam, Chrislyne Poniman, Ania Filus, Agnes Sumargi & Lia Boediman	Parenting Style, Child Emotion Regulation and Behavioral Problems: The Moderating Role of Cultural Values in Australia and Indonesia	Cross sectional study	The results showed that parenting patterns were significantly related to children's emotional regulation and behavioral problems. Emotion regulation was better ($b \frac{1}{4} 0.13$, $p < 0.01$) and behavior problems were lower ($b \frac{1}{4} -0.13$, $p < 0.05$) in children with authoritative parenting, while authoritarian parents were associated with

				poorer emotion regulation ($b = -0.21, p < 0.001$) and higher behavior problems ($b = 0.23, p < 0.001$) in children (7).
6.	Keshia B. Wagers, M.A. and Elizabeth J. Kiel, Ph.D.	The Influence of Parenting and Temperament on Empathy Development in Toddlers	Longitudinal study	Authoritative parenting, warmth and reasoning are related to children's empathy. Authoritative parenting is significantly related to empathy in children with low temperamental levels but not in children with high temperamental levels. This also applies to warmth and reasoning given by parents to their children (8).
7.	Miran Lavrič and Andrej Naterer	The power of authoritative parenting: A cross-national study of effects of exposure to different parenting styles on life satisfaction	A cross-national study	There is a positive and strong correlation between authoritative parenting and adolescent life satisfaction, while authoritarian and permissive parenting tend to be weak or not correlated with adolescent life satisfaction (9).
8.	Agnes Maria Sumargi, Eli Prasetyo and Benedicta Winona Ardeli	PARENTING STYLES AND THEIR IMPACTS ON CHILD PROBLEM BEHAVIORS	Multiple regression analyses	Fathers' and mothers' parenting styles as predictors of children's behavioral and emotional problems (10).
9.	Carlos Salavera, Pablo Usán, and Alberto Quilez-Robres	Exploring the Effect of Parental Styles on Social Skills: The Mediating Role of Affects	Lateral design	Parenting style affects social skills, where high social skills lead to parents with democratic or authoritative parenting, while permissive parenting produces a negative impact on social skills (11).
10.	Ellen H. Steele and Cliff McKinney	Emerging adult psychological problems and parenting style: Moderation by parent-child relationship quality	Cross-sectional study	The insignificant direct effect of authoritative parenting style on newborn adults internalizing and externalizing problems (12).
11.	Dan Gao, Junsheng Liu, Amanda Bullock, Dan Li and Xinyin Chen	Transactional models linking maternal authoritative parenting, child self-esteem, and approach coping strategies	Longitudinal panel design	The results show that child self-esteem significantly influences children's approach coping strategies through maternal authoritative parenting (13).

3.1. Authoritative parenting style on cognitive development

Parenting is the attitude of parents when dealing with children's emotions such as crying, aggression, lying or showing less competence in education, as a form of responsibility (4). Authoritative parenting is positively related to children's cognitive development, while the opposite relationship is shown by authoritarian parenting. This is because authoritative parents provide a balance between high demands on children and high responsiveness by parents (5). Authoritative parenting is proven to be the best parenting pattern in improving academic achievement at school compared to other parenting patterns. The results showed that authoritative parenting has a positive effect on academic achievement because the quality of interaction and authoritative parenting will bring out the courage, motivation and responsibility of children in facing their future (4).

3.2. Authoritative parenting style on behavior problems

Parents with authoritative parenting reported that children have lower difficulties and problems than children with authoritarian parenting (1). This study found that authoritarian parenting is rarely used by mothers and fathers, who

use authoritative parenting more often will reduce children's behavior problems. Authoritative parenting from the father can prevent and overcome problematic child behavior, such as irritability, fighting, whining, resisting, and other disruptive behaviors (10). This is related to children's low perception of the difficulties they experience because authoritative parenting has an indirect protective effect (1). In line with other research that behavioral problems are lower in children with authoritative parenting, while authoritarian parents are associated with higher behavioral problems in children (7).

3.3. Authoritative parenting style on career decision self-efficacy of adolescents

Career decision self-efficacy of adolescents is a person's ability to make important career-related decisions that are influenced by parenting, thinking style, and gender. Parenting influences a person's thinking style and has a direct impact on the process of determining individual career planning and development. Career decision self-efficacy of adolescents is influenced by authoritative parenting because authoritative parents generally set clear rules and boundaries, but still allow democratic discussions within the family. Thus, there is a balance between parental warmth and control so that adolescents have high aspects in terms of: self-assessment, occupational information, goal selection, planning, and problem solving (6).

3.4. Authoritative parenting style on empathy development

Empathy is the ability to understand and position oneself as another individual. Authoritative parents show warm, responsive and supportive behaviors and attitudes that affect the development of children's empathy. Given the warmth provided by the mother is considered an example or role model and encourages children's adaptive behavior to empathize. A decrease in empathic behavior is associated with lower levels of maternal warmth and involvement, while stability and increased empathic behavior are associated with higher levels of maternal warmth (8).

3.5. Authoritative parenting style on life satisfaction

The quality of parenting has a significant impact on adolescent life satisfaction. Authoritative parenting, which involves setting rules while being responsive to a child's needs, is strongly correlated with higher levels of life satisfaction. On the other hand, authoritarian and permissive parenting styles have weak or no correlation with adolescent life satisfaction. Interestingly, it is the lack of authoritative elements in parenting rather than the presence of permissive or authoritarian styles that negatively affects life satisfaction. Research shows that exposure to authoritative parenting early in life significantly influences higher levels of satisfaction in youth. Furthermore, across countries, a combination of authoritarian and permissive parenting styles does not consistently impact life satisfaction, except in ten countries where a purely authoritarian parenting style has a strong negative impact. Therefore, a combination of authoritative parenting with permissive and authoritarian styles is needed in most countries to positively influence life satisfaction (9).

3.6. Authoritative parenting style on social skills

The results of the study in terms of positive influence on social skills were more influenced by the democratic parenting style which had a moderate but higher score compared to other parenting styles. In this case, the democratic style is the best parenting style in terms of children's social skills because parental authority is not perceived by children as something rigid but voluntarily, resulting in high scores in terms of self-concept, self-esteem and social skills and even democratic parenting style offers the best solution for children's social skills that are not allowed (11).

3.7. Authoritative parenting style emotional problem

Authoritative parenting from mothers results in better quality of mother-child relationships so that authoritative parenting in this relationship is more protective of girls' internalizing and externalizing problems, but does not apply to poor quality of mother-child relationships. This also applies to authoritative parenting between fathers and children. However, the consequences of father-daughter relationship quality and externalizing problems are more complex than those of internalizing problems (12).

3.8. Authoritative parenting style on self esteem and approach coping strategies

The results showed that mother's authoritative parenting one year later is influenced by self-esteem which in turn has an impact on the use of approach coping strategies. Children who are authoritatively parented will tend to ask for help and accept parental advice regarding how to adaptively cope with problems such as seeking support and problem solving. In line with the findings of this study, it shows that problems tend to be responded to by children with high levels of self-esteem with approach coping strategies through the family environment with approach coping strategies through an authoritative family environment (13).

4. Conclusion

Authoritative parenting is a parenting style that emphasizes parent-child affection with positive learning development. In a number of studies, authoritative parenting style is associated with various aspects of individual development. This study shows that authoritative parenting is associated with cognitive development, behavior problems, career decision self-efficacy of adolescents, empathy development, life satisfaction, social skills, emotional problems, self-esteem and approach coping strategies.

Compliance with ethical standards

Acknowledgements

This article did not receive assistance from the government, private companies, or non-profit organization.

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

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